

Inclusive primary healthcare in the community: stakeholder consultation to guide service implementation

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Abstract

Societal changes in terms of healthcare needs and availability of healthcare professionals call for adaptations in the organisation of primary healthcare. Citizens can help to design integrated health, care, and community services, hereby aligning policies and services to communities' needs. However, stakeholder consultation is often limited and does not sufficiently take health literacy into account. By joining forces between local communities and living labs, several methodologies can be set up to gain insight into the healthcare needs and expectations of citizens and care professionals to guide future-oriented and innovative public care. The current paper describes a study that took place in the municipality of Vorselaar in Belgium. In the first phase, a survey study included a sample of 1078 participants from the local community to provide insight into user needs for primary healthcare practice and preventive initiatives as well as the health literacy of the population. Recruitment activities focused on engaging a sample that reflected the local diversity and, therefore, also actively lowered participation thresholds by e.g., sending personal invitations and providing support in completing the online or pen-and-paper survey. In a second phase, co-creation sessions with citizens, (care) professionals, and more vulnerable residents were initiated to get more in-depth information about primary healthcare needs. Results indicated the need for interdisciplinary care centres with GPs, dentists, nurses, psychologists, dieticians, and social workers, and showed that citizens believe that the local government has a role to play in health promotion related to e.g., healthy food, exercising, and mental health. Health literacy in this local community was varied, covering the full range of the

spectrum, and proved to be associated with age, education, general and mental health, and loneliness. The co-creation activities led to concrete ideas for regional strategic actions to promote high-quality primary care. The current study showed that targeted recruitment for a comprehensive survey and co-creation sessions allowed for the inclusion of a large and rich sample to inform on local healthcare needs and define priorities for the local government. Residents and care professionals can be motivated and interesting partners in designing futureproof and inclusive primary healthcare.

Key words

Living Lab, co-creation, health literacy, primary healthcare, health prevention, citizen participation

Introduction

Societal changes in terms of healthcare needs and availability of healthcare professionals (e.g., in rural areas) call for adaptations in the organisation of public healthcare. Instead of being passive recipients, citizens can help to design integrated health, care and community services, hereby improving municipalities' accountability and aligning policies and services to communities' needs (Conklin et al., 2015; De Weger et al., 2022). However, while the 'stronger and more active citizens' are regularly involved in participation, more vulnerable residents are overlooked (Glimmerveen et al., 2019). Also relevant in this respect is that these more vulnerable individuals are more likely to have lower health literacy (Sørensen et al., 2015). To ensure the provision of high-quality healthcare, it is important to tailor communication and service provision to the health literacy of the entire target population. Health literacy is defined as "people's knowledge, motivation and competencies to access, understand, appraise, and apply health information in order to make judgments and take decisions in everyday life concerning healthcare, disease prevention and health promotion to maintain or improve quality of life during the life course" (Sørensen et al., 2012). Lower health literacy has been associated with poorer health conditions, unhealthy behaviours, and less use of preventive services (Berkman et al., 2011; Fernandez et al., 2016; Jayasinghe et al., 2016; Sørensen et al., 2015; Von Wagner et al., 2007). Promoting health literacy is, therefore, important. Studies indicate that promoting health literacy not only reduces healthcare costs (McCray, 2005), but also has important health benefits, both on an individual level as well as on a societal level (Nutbeam, 2000). In addition, health literacy has been recognised as a key factor for reducing health inequality (Sørensen et al., 2013).

Local governments often do not have the necessary expertise to perform the required inclusive and large-scale stakeholder consultation for healthcare reorganisation. However, they could get support from local living labs. Living labs are open innovation ecosystems with expertise in the inclusion of end-user populations and the execution of such large-scale data collection in the context of exploration and co-creation of innovations (De Witte et al., 2021). Additionally, living labs focus on the testing and upscaling of innovative solutions, granting value to the involved stakeholders. The current study concerns a collaboration between a municipality and a living lab with the goal of shaping future primary healthcare. The study has two main aims: (1) gaining insight into the local user needs for an interdisciplinary primary healthcare practice and preventive initiatives as well as the health literacy in a representative sample of the

population, and (2) obtaining more in-depth qualitative data from three distinct stakeholder groups, i.e., citizens, care professionals and more vulnerable residents (e.g., citizens with lower socio-economic status), to formulate concrete and tangible goals for the organisation of healthcare and prevention.

The study took place in the municipality of Vorselaar in Belgium where healthcare provision was under severe pressure due to a retirement wave in healthcare professionals, more specifically GPs and dentists. Residents were forced to look for alternatives in the wider region or postpone essential care. Therefore, the municipality wanted to create an open interdisciplinary healthcare network, putting the focus on prevention and close cooperation between different actors in the health and care sector, and established a primary healthcare practice. The study took place in two phases, namely a large survey-based citizen consultation and a qualitative small-scale co-creation phase for further reflection and enrichment of the data.

Phase 1: The Health Survey

Method

Recruitment

All residents of Vorselaar aged 18 and above were invited to participate in the study through a personal invitation in their letterbox, signed by the mayor. To lower participation thresholds, a paper version of the survey was enclosed. However, citizens were encouraged to complete the survey online, using a QR code or website link. Reminders to fill in the survey were provided on paper through the local newspaper, online on the website and social media profiles of the municipality, and in person through flyers distributed at the annual fair. Special attention was given to the inclusion of more vulnerable residents by e.g., sending personal invitations to every adult inhabitant and providing support in completing the online or pen-and-paper survey on different locations (such as the town hall, local service centre or even at home). Recruitment and data collection took place during 2 months in the summer of 2022. The Study was approved by the Social and Societal Ethics Committee SMEC of KU Leuven (G-2022 06 2111) and all participants provided informed consent.

Health survey

The survey consisted of three themes in addition to the demographical information (age, gender, education, and income): health and well-being (including general health,

mental health, and loneliness), health literacy, and needs and preferences related to health prevention and a local primary healthcare practice. The survey included both existing (previously validated) scales and novel survey items, when no suitable existing instruments could be identified. The 6-item De Jong Gierveld loneliness scale calculates a score between 0 and 6 with higher scores representing more loneliness (De Jong Gierveld & van Tilburg, 2008). The scale has good internal consistency in the current sample, $\alpha = .84$. The Dutch translation of the short version of the European Health Literacy Questionnaire allows to calculate a total score ranging from 12 to 48, with higher values representing better health literacy (HLS-Q12; Finbråten et al., 2018). This 12-item questionnaire has good reliability ($\alpha = .89$) and is conceptually conceived as a matrix of four cognitive domains (access, understand, appraise, and apply health information) and three health domains (health care, disease prevention, and health promotion). Five-point Likert scales were used to assess (mental) health. The level of education was measured with 6 categories from no degree to university degree. Income was defined on a 5-point Likert reflecting the extent to which household income could cover all expenses, ranging from very easy to very difficult.

Data Analysis

Data were analysed using SPSS 28.0 (IBM SPSS Statistics). Associations between different variables were calculated using Kendall tau (τ) correlations. Hierarchical regression analyses were used to assess to which extent demographic and health variables predicted health literacy. In advance, categorical variables were dichotomised and differences in health literacy across demographic or health factors were examined using independent t-tests. All variables showing significant t-tests were entered in the hierarchical regression analyses. Ranking questions were analysed using Friedman ANOVA. Open-ended questions were analysed through thematic analyses. Sample sizes can differ between analyses due to missing values.

Results

A total of 1078 inhabitants of the municipality completed the survey, of which 728 did so online. This corresponds to a response rate of 16.5%. When comparing the sample to data from the Belgian bureau of statistics, we achieved in covering the diversity within the community. Sample characteristics showed a good distribution in age (from 18 up to 80+), professional situation, and income. Nevertheless, the sample included slightly more women (60.6%), and showed fairly high education levels.

Health and well-being

On average, respondents reported satisfactory general and mental health (see Figure 1). A minority stated to be in (very) poor general ($n = 58/1064$) or mental health ($n = 62/1049$). Feelings of loneliness were present to some extent in 50% of the respondents ($n = 544/1023$), with about 7% attaining the maximum score ($n = 72/1023$). Table 1 shows that lower general and mental health were related to lower income, lower levels of education and more loneliness. General health also correlated with age, with increasing age being associated with a decrease in self-reported health. Mental health nor loneliness were related to inhabitants' age ($\tau = -.00, p = .89$ and $\tau = .04, p = .12$, respectively).

Figure 1. General and mental health

Table 1. Correlations (Kendall τ) between demographical and health variables.

	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Loneliness	1					
<i>N</i>	995					
2. Age	.04	1				
<i>N</i>	956	993				
3. Education	-.13*	-.33*	1			
<i>N</i>	995	993	1036			
4. Income	.26*	.09*	-.29*	1		
<i>N</i>	984	977	1019	1019		
5. General health	.24*	.13*	-.13*	.24*	1	
<i>N</i>	992	988	1030	1016	103	
6. Mental health	.38*	-.00	-.10*	.25*	.49*	1
<i>N</i>	994	976	1018	1004	101	1018
7. Health literacy	-.26*	-.16*	.19*	-.19*	-.21*	-.22*
<i>N</i>	910	893	923	916	920	919

Note. * $p < .001$.

Health literacy

The sample obtained a mean health literacy score of 34.04 ($SD = 5.13$, range 12-48, Figure 2). Health literacy showed a positive correlation with education and correlated negatively with loneliness, age, income, general health, and mental health (Table 1).

Figure 2. Health literacy scores ($N = 945$)

Independent variables were included in the hierarchical regression in 5 steps (Table 2). Assumptions of multicollinearity, normality of residuals, and homoscedasticity were not violated. Model 4 provides the best fit, explaining 16.3% of the total variance in health literacy. Age, education, general and mental health, and loneliness are unique predictors for health literacy, whereas no additional contribution was found for gender or income. The direction of effects showed that health literacy was lower in individuals with higher age, lower education, lower general and mental health, and higher scores for loneliness.

Table 2. Hierarchical regression analysis for the dependent variable health literacy.

	R²	R²_{adjusted}	ΔR²	Standardised β-coefficient
Model 1	0.07	0.07	0.07**	
Age				-0.16**
Gender				-0.04
Education				0.18**
Model 2	0.10	0.10	0.03**	
Age				-0.14**
Gender				-0.04
Education				0.17**
General health				0.17**
Model 3	0.14	0.13	0.03**	
Age				-0.15**
Gender				-0.05
Education				0.16**
General health				0.08*
Mental health				0.20**
Model 4	0.16	0.16	0.03**	
Age				-0.15**
Gender				-0.05
Education				0.15**
General health				0.07*
Mental health				0.15**
Loneliness				-0.17**
Model 5	0.17	0.16	0.003	
Age				-0.15**
Gender				-0.05
Education				0.14**
General health				0.06
Mental health				0.14**
Loneliness				-0.16**
Income				0.06

Note. R² is the proportion of variance explained by the model. R²_{adjusted} is an estimation of the variance explained on population level. ΔR² verifies whether a model is a significant better fit compared to the previous model. Standardised β shows the unique contribution of each variable. *p < .05; ** p < .001.

Needs and preferences regarding health prevention and a local primary healthcare practice

Participants ranked several lifestyle factors according to the influence they can have on health outcomes (Table 3). Healthy food was perceived as the most important factor regarding health prevention, followed by exercise, mental health, and sleep. There were only minor differences in ranking across age groups. People over 80 attributed a bit more influence on sleep compared to mental health and individuals under 60 ranked smoking before alcohol consumption.

Table 3. Participants' ranking of the extent to which lifestyle factors influence health.

Health factors	Mean rank
Healthy food	2.05
Exercise	2.62
Mental health	3.43
Sleep	3.55
Alcohol consumption	4.71
Smoking	4.87

Note. Lower mean rank represents higher perceived influence on health.

Most residents believed that the local government has a role to play in health prevention. This was reflected in a score of 7.10 ($SD = 2.36$, $N = 1018$) on an 11-point rating scale (0 = *not at all*; 10 = *definitely*). An open question regarding this topic revealed that motivating, stimulating, and activating residents is the most important task, followed by informing people on prevention through thematic sessions, providing health articles in the local newspaper, etc. In third place, they mentioned the need to involve a sufficient number of affordable general practitioners, dentists and paramedics in the primary healthcare practice in order to make health (promotion) accessible to all inhabitants.

The majority of the respondents (96.81%) has a 'family doctor' or a regular general practitioner (GP) to visit when needed. However, this GP is situated outside of the municipality for two-thirds of inhabitants. Factors that play a role in GP selection are (ranked from most to least important): (1) being able to access GP quickly, (2) physical distance, (3) recommendations from friends or family, (4) GP as part of a group practice, (5) other. Common self-reported other factors consist of having a relationship of trust with the GP ($N = 137$), competency ($N = 81$) and empathy ($N = 45$) of the GP, communicative skills ($N = 29$), and providing sufficient time for patients ($N = 26$).

Participants selected their top 5 of preferred disciplines for an interdisciplinary

primary healthcare practice out of a list of 13 care professions (Table 4). For the five most listed professions their mean rank was taken into account to determine an overall top 5. Adding a dentist to the primary practice was considered most essential, followed by a nurse, psychologist, dietician, and a social worker. Results were similar across age groups.

Table 4. Preferred health professions for the primary healthcare practice in addition to the general practitioner.

Care profession	N	Mean rank
Dentist	869	1.31
Nurse	392	2.29
Psychologist	532	2.52
Dietician	263	3.17
Social worker	275	3.29
Burn-out coach	191	3.45
Medical secretary	184	2.64
Occupational therapist	182	3.38
Speech therapist	170	3.50
Move-by-referral coach	85	3.25
Midwife	82	3.33
Sexologist	37	3.81
Smoking cessation counsellor	19	3.32

Note. N is the number of times a particular profession is mentioned in the top 5. Lower mean rank indicates a higher need to include the profession in the healthcare practice. Physiotherapists were not included in the list because this group is already well represented in the municipality.

Phase 2: Co-creation sessions with different stakeholders

Method

Recruitment

Recruitment aimed to include citizens, care professionals, and more vulnerable residents of whom we expect lower health literacy (e.g., citizens with lower socio-economic status). We aimed to include about eight to ten individuals per group, with a minimum of four individuals for the harder to reach samples (in line with Carlsen & Glenton, 2011). Citizens were recruited through targeted emails to the group of respondents of the survey that had indicated to be willing to participate in follow-up research. Batches of approximately 10 emails were sent every two days until we reached a satisfactory number of participants for this session. We aimed to include a balanced ratio of males/females and participants of different age groups. All care

professionals active in the municipality were invited for participation by the local government through email. Finally, more vulnerable residents with assumably limited health literacy were recruited with the help of a local organisation that focusses on inclusion of vulnerable people in society (e.g., older adults, citizens with lower socio-economic status). The study was approved by the Social and Societal Ethics Committee SMEC of KU Leuven (G-2022 06 2111) and all participants provided informed consent.

Co-creation

The goal of the co-creation sessions was to enrich the findings of the health survey and to generate ideas for the future local health strategy. For this purpose, the GPS brainstorm kit (Flanders DC, Figure 3) for idea generation was used in all three sessions. This is a structured brainstorming method based on presenting five relevant subthemes related to the vision and strategy of the upcoming interdisciplinary healthcare practice, represented by the overarching statement ‘The healthcare practice is an open, inviting environment for anyone with questions about health, care and well-being’. Additionally, a sixth residual subtheme or free field, in our sessions called ‘the sky is the limit’, encouraged participants to think out-of-the box and to come up with innovative ideas without restrictions in time and money. The generated ideas were prioritised. For citizens and more vulnerable individuals with assumably limited health literacy the following five themes were used: preventive health, inform and learn, open for everyone, inviting meeting place, and new building 2024. For the care professionals the focus was a little different and included the themes preventive health, primary healthcare, enhancing health literacy, interdisciplinary, and partner network.

Procedure

All sessions took place in October or November of 2022. Every co-creation session started with an ice-breaker game. This animation technique made participants more conducive to creativity and sharing, and aims to relax the atmosphere. Then both the primary healthcare practice and the living lab were introduced. Next, the GPS brainstorm was applied. Participants successively discussed the six subthemes regarding the upcoming primary healthcare practice in small groups. Every idea was written on a separate post-it. Afterwards, ideas were prioritised with all participants. In case there was still time left in the 2-hour session, the prioritised ideas were substantively elaborated.

Data analysis

All ideas (post-its) were prioritised by the participants. The moderators of the sessions

combined the insights of all three sessions into practice-oriented advices.

Results

Citizens

Ten citizens were included. Participants indicated that the local government should target health promotion to inhabitants of all life stages, starting at a school context. The primary healthcare practice should be easily accessible and affordable for all citizens. Different online and offline contact options should be available flexibly (daytime, evening, weekend). The healthcare practice is recommended to not only accommodate doctors and paramedics but to be a multifunctional room where also workshops or thematic sessions regarding health-related topics can be hosted. Examples consist of yoga or work-out sessions, workshops to enhance individuals' computer/digital skills, social media training, and first aid trainings. Participants also had several suggestions concerning the design of the new building. Citizens recommended to include plenty of natural light, art of local artists, a children's corner, a stable internet connection, a large parking lot nearby, and some benches for informal talks.

Figure 3. Using the GPS brainstorm kit in co-creation with citizens

Care professionals

Fifteen local care professionals from nine different disciplines agreed to participate (out

of 51 municipality care professionals; response rate 29%). They acknowledged that cooperation across disciplines was limited at the time. Online information on local care professionals was often outdated and they, therefore, felt the need to get acquainted with each other and each other's expertise. Better interrelations would also facilitate referral between the disciplines. One suggestion was to build an online platform with updated information of all care professionals of the municipality. Care professionals wanted to prioritise inclusion of vulnerable individuals but found it a challenging subject to tackle on their own. Therefore, they suggested to get together quarterly to exchange ideas on different health themes, including how to strengthen residents' health literacy. However, one concern that emerged was the funding of health promotion activities. Dissemination of events or thematic sessions could use the proposed platform or website of the primary healthcare practice. Participants also stressed the importance of attracting enough dentists for the primary care practice, as the municipality had lacked a dentist for several years already. Finally, targeting schools for health prevention was considered an important step to start early with the introduction of healthy life habits. This entails the additional advantage that school children can act as a gateway for providing information to parents who might be more difficult to reach, such as parents with a migration background or lower socio-economic status.

Vulnerable residents

Five vulnerable residents could be recruited. One of the inclusion coordinators of the inclusion organisation also participated in the session. Participants indicated that the best way to improve accessibility for vulnerable participants is through personal contact. However, these people often tend to live in isolation. Since doctors are not allowed to advertise their services (in line with the Belgian law), the participants suggested that volunteers affiliated with the primary care practice could go door-to-door to inform about the services of the healthcare practice. These volunteers could work with informal district leaders who are aware of specific difficulties in the neighbourhood. In terms of the design of materials, leaflets for health prevention activities should be playful rather than pedantic, with concrete tips and tricks. Preventive initiatives could be conceptualised as group challenges that are rewarded. Furthermore, participants also indicated that the primary health practice should be easily accessible, e.g., for wheelchairs or rollators, and touch screens at the entrance should preferably be avoided as they are a burden to the visually impaired. The practice should have extensive opening hours but additionally, offer GP home visits since they are essential for those who are less mobile. One should be able to make an appointment

online or by phone. A warm welcome was deemed important as they indicated that the primary healthcare practice should have a cosy reception with friendly staff that help without prejudice. The idea of a coffee corner as a meeting place was also suggested. Finally, the participants would like the primary healthcare practice and the local government to organise workshops for citizens to improve both digital and health literacy skills.

Discussion

Citizens can facilitate change in a range of health, care, and community services (Conklin et al., 2015). In line with Milewa et al. (2002), who indicate increased awareness of strategic public and patient involvement in primary healthcare planning and organisation, the present study was designed to co-create a futureproof primary healthcare strategy with an open interdisciplinary healthcare network, putting the focus on prevention and close cooperation between different actors in the health and care sector. The current work describes a partnership between a living lab and a local government to organise an inclusive and large-scale stakeholder consultation for healthcare reorganisation.

Findings indicated that citizens of Vorselaar were generally in reasonably good health. Lower general and mental health were related to lower income, lower levels of education and more loneliness, which is consistent with previous research (Klein et al., 2021; Quadt et al., 2020; Veenstra & Vanzella-Yang, 2020). The sample showed varying levels of health literacy and analyses revealed that lower health literacy was associated with higher age, lower education, lower general and mental health, and more loneliness, in line with previous work (Musich et al., 2015; Paasche-Orlow et al., 2005; Van Der Heide et al., 2013). Results also supported a need for accessible interdisciplinary care practices with GPs, dentists, nurses, psychologists, dieticians, and social workers. Co-creation sessions with different types of stakeholders revealed that both citizens and care professionals were willing to invest in the municipality's health landscape and led to suggestions for concrete actions concerning launching the primary care practice as well as preventive activities organised by the local government. Additionally, citizens believed the local government has a role to play in health promotion related to e.g., healthy food, exercise, and mental health.

This study reached a large sample of inhabitants of a local municipality. A comparison with governmental statistics showed that the sample was a good cross section of inhabitants of the municipality, including elderly and more vulnerable individuals. This suggests that findings are representative for the population of interest. The study also

succeeded in including almost one third of local care professionals in co-creation. By combining multiple perspectives and research activities (survey and co-creation sessions) the current study was able to gain rich insights allowing for the design of better primary healthcare in the community. While findings regarding health literacy, (mental) health and related characteristics are in line with existing evidence, other findings and preferences will likely be driven by the local context and cannot directly be generalized beyond this municipality. Another limitation concerns the cross-sectional nature of the study, which makes establishing causal directionality difficult.

The pressing shortage of care professionals in the rather small municipality provided a suitable context to design innovative local healthcare services from scratch. The current study will shape the healthcare organisation in this municipality. A detailed report of the co-creation activities was shared with the local government for the implementation and further development of ideas regarding the primary healthcare practice or preventive health initiatives in the municipality. At present, the local government has set up a prevention working group that aims to implement the suggested preventive initiatives in a sustainable way. Furthermore, the health promotion strategy is planned to be embedded in a new methodology concerning caring neighbourhoods that is being deployed in different Belgian municipalities. The current study has also led to additional collaborations between the municipality and the living lab, the latter of which is organising trainings for the municipality health professionals concerning oral and written communication in health practice (using the Memori toolkit). During these sessions, caregivers will learn how to recognize and handle health illiteracy, which is considered an important predictor for health inequity (Nutbeam & Lloyd, 2020). Trainings are followed by a network event to strengthen links between different care professionals of the municipality. In addition, the use of a digital platform for individualised health prevention is explored. In such a platform citizens could complete a set of health-related questions to obtain an overview of relevant health promotion activities organised nearby and optionally share the results directly with their GP.

Conclusion

Over the past years, an increase in research on the development of a health ecosystem approach for regional (mental) healthcare can be observed (e.g., Rosen et al., 2020). Such an approach will lead to better care and benefit both citizens and health professionals. However, an important challenge for health promotion and healthcare proves to be health literacy, which is lower in vulnerable individuals, e.g., elderly or lonely individuals and patients with (mental) health problems. This should be taken into account by policy makers and health and care professionals when designing high-

quality primary care in the community. The current study also shows that a living lab approach including a large stakeholder consultation and co-creation delivers relevant insights that facilitate the redesign of healthcare services in the community and guide implementation efforts. Interesting avenues for future research are situated in conducting localised implementation research into health promotion interventions, with special attention to the inclusion of vulnerable citizens. As a next step, such successful health promotion interventions may be deployed in larger health networks or even at a national level. Taken together, the current study shows that partnerships between living labs and local governments are promising in assessing municipality needs in terms of reorganisation of primary healthcare and implementing local preventive initiatives supported by society.

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